

Automated Feeding System for Pig Production

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Automated feeding system for pig production in Galicia (NW Spain).

Pig production has becoming an important source of various livestock food products that are currently produced in large scale macrofarms where livestock welfare is compromise and large environment negative impacts linked to the concentrated production of ammonia but also nitrates are generated. Extensive farming systems may overcome these macrofarm intensive pork products production linked to high quality product production based on understory plant production in forests as is carried out in the dehesas or in some Galician pig farms. However, extensified farms have an important inconvenient linked to labour needs that makes the costs too high to make pig production farming systems based on forest not economically viable. ASOPORCEL the Galician farm association has developed an automated feeding system for pig production. The extensive feed production system is based on the Paulov principle that associate a sound with the delivery of feed in and automated way that concentrates all animals in a small recint where camaras are placed to provide pig information to the farmer every day without being in the farm. The system is completely autonomic from an energy point of view due to the connection to solar panels.

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